

**THE IMPORTANCE OF AUDITS IN ENSURING THE
FINANCIAL STABILITY OF BUSINESS ENTITIES****Sobirov Otabek Olimjonovich****Doctor of Economics (DSc), Associate Professor,****Namangan State Technical University.****Associate Professor of the Department of Accounting****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20176456>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 08th May 2026Accepted: 09th May 2026Online: 14th May 2026**KEYWORDS***Enterprises, financial stability, audit, financial statements, small business, international economic space, investments.***ABSTRACT***This article discusses the role and importance of audit in ensuring the financial stability of enterprises today. It also discusses the relevance of transparent financial reporting by enterprises. In addition, recommendations are given to ensure the financial stability of enterprises.*

In the period when the world economy is developing rapidly, the reforms being implemented in our republic to form a stable economy are showing their positive results. In particular, in a short period of time, in implementing deep structural changes in the economy, ensuring growth in population incomes, strengthening effective foreign trade and investment processes, reforming agriculture, and in the sustainable development of small business and private entrepreneurship, financial statement auditing has become one of the main factors in achieving significant achievements in strengthening their activities. Because accurate and correct preparation of financial statements is one of the main factors in attracting investment funds today.

The prestige and position of our republic in the international economic arena is steadily increasing due to the audit of financial statements of economic entities and the strengthening of financial activities. At present, the socio-economic development of countries of the world differs sharply in its meaning and content from previous stages. The most important and fundamental aspect of this is the increasing integration and globalization of national economies. At the same time, these processes also affect the intensification of competition in the international arena, the intensification of the struggle of economic entities of each country to strengthen their financial position.

However, it should be noted that, along with the positive aspects of integration and globalization into the world economy, there are also certain contradictory aspects. In particular, the unevenness of economic development in different countries, that is, the unreliability of the information reflected in the financial statements of enterprises and organizations, the incorrect use of funds received from various activities, and the lack of accurate reflection of international currency and credit relations in accounting, lead to differences in socio-economic development between countries of the world and hinder the sustainable development of the world economy as a whole. Also, another characteristic aspect of these processes is that socio-economic shocks occurring in one country of the world inevitably affect other countries.

As is known, in recent years, a number of positive works have been carried out on the formation and development of auditing activities. In 2021, the Law “On Auditing Activities” in a new edition was adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In order to implement this law and ensure that audit conclusions are taken into account by tax and other supervisory authorities, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Improving Auditing Activities and Increasing the Importance of Audit Inspections” and a number of other regulatory documents were adopted, and the procedures for conducting certification for the right to engage in auditing activities and issuing licenses for auditing activities were established.

When determining current and future measures for the socio-economic development of our country, we must comprehensively take into account the impact of the global financial crisis, formulate economic development programs from the perspective of the impact of these processes and consistently implement them.

It is very important for each of the production enterprises operating in our country to organize their activities correctly. Audits are of great importance in coordinating the activities of production enterprises. This is because constant audit control of the financial condition of enterprises will help the enterprise achieve its strategic goals in the future.

As everyone knows, ensuring financial stability is always a difficult and costly process. In production entities, the activities of departments are carried out according to strictly established norms. However, in many cases, deviations from the established costs occur in the production of products. Such situations mainly lead to negative results. Such negative situations are almost never encountered in enterprises that have a constant audit control system.

One of the urgent issues in ensuring the financial stability of enterprises operating in our country is ensuring that their activities are audited.

In conclusion, we consider it advisable to implement these processes:

1. Conducting constant control over the accuracy of the information reflected in the financial statements of enterprises and organizations;
2. Ensuring systematic control over the correct use of funds received from various activities;
3. Drawing up and maintaining financial statements based on the requirements of international standards;
4. Providing auditors with modern information and communication technologies and a high-quality material and technical base when organizing audits at enterprises;
5. Constantly familiarizing themselves with the latest regulatory legal acts and improving legal skills;
6. Accurate reflection of international currency and credit relations in accounting and preventing differences in socio-economic development between countries of the world create the basis for the sustainable development of the world economy as an integrated system.

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